

EXPLORING MOMENT-FORM IN GENERATIVE MUSIC

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ABSTRACT

Generative art is art created through the use of a system. A unique and distinguishing characteristic of generative artworks is that they change with each run of the system; in the case of generative music, a musical composition that re-explores itself, continually producing alternative versions. An open problem in generative music is large-scale structure: how can generative systems avoid creating music that meanders aimlessly, yet doesn't require strict architectural forms into which it is forced inside? *Moments* is a generative installation that explores Moment-form, a term Stockhausen coined to describe (his) music that avoids directed narrative curves. Through the use of musebots – independent musical agents – that utilise a *parameterBot* to generate an overall template of “moments”, the agents communicate their intentions and coordinate conditions for collaborative machine composition.

1. INTRODUCTION

Generative art refers to art that has been created with the use of a system. Such artist-designed systems make decisions that are normally made by the artist. Galanter points out that this type of art has a long tradition, and such approaches may be “as old as art itself” [1]. Metacreation is the contemporary approach to generative art, and looks at all aspects of the creative process and their potential for systematic exploration through software. This field is populated by a diverse group of people – psychologists, art theorists, cognitive scientists, artificial intelligence researchers, machine learning specialists, and, perhaps most importantly, artists. Musical Metacreation (MuMe) has proven to be a fertile creative domain for composers exploring new avenues of production.

1.1 Musical Metacreation (MuMe)

Galanter's definition of generative art [1] – “any art practice where the artist uses a system... which is set into motion with some degree of autonomy *contributing to or resulting in a completed work of art*” (italics mine) – assumes a fully finished artwork. Furthermore, implicit in this definition is that the system may involve human interaction, in that the system need only *contribute* to the final work. As such, human involvement, whether through algorithm design, direct control by an operator,

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or interaction with a live human performer, has remained an active presence in the dynamic generation of music.

2. MUSICAL FORM

One reason for continued human interaction in MuMe is that generating entire musical compositions entails the development of musical form, a highly complex task [2]. Form involves the complex interaction of multiple musical structures in order to logically organise the work's progression in time. Strategies are required to organise these structures so as to “provide reference points for the listener to hold on to the piece, otherwise it may lose its sense of unity” [3].

Musical form is “the unique result of the deployment of particular materials and processes” [4]. Form is the consequence of the relationships between the various structures within the music – themselves methods of organising pitch, onsets, volume, and timbre; the surface relationships within the music – i.e. the selection and resulting relationships between individual musical objects at a given point in time – can be considered its design [after 5].

Kramer suggests that one difficulty in conceptualising form is due to its inherent role in organising time. While theories exist dealing with rhythm and meter, “more difficult to discuss are motion, continuity, progression, pacing, proportion, duration, and tempo” [6], all aspects to do with musical form. Schoenberg expressed the complexity of form, stating that it requires “logic and coherence” in order for a musical composition to be perceived as being comprehensible, but that its elements also should function “like those of a living organism” [7]. The difficulty for composers is achieving a balance between strict structures that appears logical, with an organic element that engenders surprise.

2.1 Generating Form

This difficulty is multiplied exponentially when applied to generative music: how can one codify structural decisions when many of these decisions are aesthetic in nature? For example, interactive systems allow the composer to determine when to move to the next section, or when to alter a process, based upon choices informed by context – how long has the current section been going on? – and aesthetics – is the material starting to lose interest? Different surface features (i.e. the musical context) will engender different decisions; codifying such pro-

cesses suggests the need for computational aesthetic evaluation, a highly complex notion that remains an open problem [8].

Nevertheless, MuMe has produced a variety of heuristic solutions to the problem of generating structure. Previous computational models of musical structure include Cypher [9], Experiments in Musical Intelligence [10], GESMI [11], the use of statistical prediction [e.g. 12], the use of machine learning techniques [e.g. 13], and agent negotiation [e.g. 14].

Two contrasting methodologies have dominated the field: top-down versus bottom-up methods. The former relies upon architectural models that may be pre-generated in varying degrees: Cope's use of SPEAC is one such example [15], as well as GESMI's structures derived from a corpus of dance music [11]. Bottom-up approaches, which Boulez described as "form from material" [16], entail methods of self-organisation [17]. Narmour [18] provides a useful discussion on the interaction and opposition of these two approaches in musical composition.

3. NON-TELEOLOGICAL MUSICAL FORM

A clear difficulty in generating structure, as pointed out above, results from adopting the complex procedures (i.e. goal-directedness) from functional tonality. Tonality, the overriding organisational structure of music from 1600-1900 (and continuing today in many styles), is the music of continuity and motion. With the dissolution of functional tonality in the early 20th century, composers were forced to search for other methods of goal-directed motion. While composers such as Schoenberg attempted to construct new methods for continuity – provoking the adage "new wine in old bottles" – Stravinsky investigated non-developmental methods as early as *Le Sacre* (1913), and discontinuity in *Symphonies of Wind Instruments* (1920)

Similarly, Debussy (*Jeux*, 1913), Webern (*Symphony*, second movement, 1928), Varèse (*Ionisation*, 1931), and Messiaen (*Quatuor pour la fin du temps*, 1941) composed music that seemingly avoided forward motion and favoured discontinuity between sections. By the 1960s, these ideas were overtly adopted by Cage in his time frames, Reich in his gradual processes, Glass in his additive processes, and, most importantly, Stockhausen in his Moment-form [19]. As Smalley suggests, "Moment-form is the only really new, linguistically independent and therefore generally applicable formal concept to have arisen since 1945" [20].

3.1 Stockhausen and Moment-form

First fully explored musically in *Momente* (1962-69), Stockhausen described the potential of Moment-form in *Texte zur Musik* in 1963:

"A given moment is not merely regarded as the consequence of the previous one and the prelude to the coming one, but as something individual, inde-

pendent and centered in itself, capable of existing on its own." [19].

Momente continued to explore musical structure from a non-pitch dominated perspective that began with *Kontakte* (1958–60). Unlike the total serialist explorations of the previous decade, which still relied upon pitch for structural elements, Stockhausen's new model derived structure "from the totality of possibilities inherent in the diverse materials which the composer brings together for each particular work" [20].

3.1.1 Requirements for Moment-form

A moment is comprised of a static entity – for example, a single harmony; moments avoid development and goal-directed behaviour, although the potential for processes to provide variation in the surface design is possible. Subsequent moments are contrasting, often dramatically, with one another, as their internal organisation and concerns must be different; as a result, changes between moments result in what Kramer refers to as discontinuity [21]. Using Salzer's definitions, described earlier, each moment contains its own structure; it can consist of a great deal of surface variation, as long as the variation does not contribute to goal-directed behaviour; the resulting combination of contrasting moments results in the final Moment-form.

Momente also uses a mobile feature in which the individual moments can be reordered in different ways, which Stockhausen refers to as polyvalent: "A composer is no longer in the position of beginning from a fixed point in time and moving forwards from it; rather he is moving in all directions within a materially circumscribed world" [20]. Because different moments must be self-contained, and are defined by contrasting states, the order of moments should not matter; however, polyvalence – the re-ordering of moments between performances – is not a requirement. As Kramer suggests, "the order of moments must *appear* arbitrary for the work to conform to the spirit of moment form" [21].

Stockhausen separates beginning and ending, from starting and stopping: the former pair he equates with dramatic (closed) forms, the latter pair with open moment forms. Although compositions need to begin and end for practical reasons, "a proper moment form will give the impression of starting in the midst of previously unheard music, and it will break off without reaching any structural cadence, as if the music goes on, inaudibly [21]. This concept gives rise to a feeling of "endlessness" within Moment-form.

3.1.2 Proportion

Kramer states that in Stravinsky's precursor to Moment-form, specifically in *Symphonies of Wind Instruments*, the motivic and tempo consistency within a section results in its self-containment and staticism; progression in the music takes place between, rather than within, moments [21]. The relative length of each moment is an integral aspect of a work's formal success, as proportional length is one of the only remaining principles of formal coherence within Moment-form [21]. Kramer analyses a number of works, demonstrating the reliance on, for example,

3:2 time ratios (which also can be considered the golden ratio, as well as the Fibonacci series)[22] between moments in the music of Stravinsky [21]; Maconie does the same for Stockhausen [23], while Parks describes the music of Debussy in terms of its proportional relationships and discontinuity [24].

3.2 Moment-form in ambient music

Kramer was considering art music and the evolving tradition leading up to Stockhausen, at almost the same time that an ambient aesthetic emerged outside of concert music. While ambient music can itself be traced back to Satie's furniture music [25], Eno popularised the music with seminal recordings in the late 1970s which were meant "to accommodate many levels of listening attention without enforcing one in particular" [26]. The result was music that avoided dramatic change and motion, and tended to preference continuity and stasis. Unlike Kramer's notion of Moment-form that relies upon discontinuity between moments for an overall structural form, ambient music most often contains only a single moment.

Adopted by the electronic dance music community in the 1990s as a "chill-out" alternative to its beat-oriented music, artists such as Aphex Twin (*Selected Ambient Works Volume II*, 1994), Boards of Canada, and KLF (*Chill Out*, 1990) produced music that often lacked strong beats (or at least the ever-present drumbeat of contemporary dance music of the time), and, more importantly in our case, repetitive formal structures [27].

Ambient electronica, and its contemporary offspring, dark- and post-ambient, continues to avoid discontinuity, preferring a relative consistency in harmony and timbre: although gestures may enter and exist – sometimes resulting in separate sub-moments in doing so – the amount of significant timbral change is relatively limited.

Such consistency underlines an integral aspect of Moment-form: staticism. Kramer poses the question "is musical staticism an experiential possibility? How long must it go on before the listener gives up expectation of change and enters a static mode of perception? The answer seems to depend on the *richness of the unchanging sound.*" [21]. In the case of contemporary ambient electronic music, a richness of timbre is perhaps its most obvious feature.

3.2.1 Christopher Bissonnette

One contemporary recording artist whose work, perhaps inadvertently, can be considered as utilising Moment-

form is Christopher Bissonnette.

Bissonnette's 2005 album *Periphery*ⁱⁱ contains 7 tracks, ranging in length from just under 5 minutes to almost ten minutes, each of which can be considered as a single moment, or several related sub-moments. The music is slow moving, lacking any obvious pulse, and uses drones without harmonic change to create a feeling of staticism.

Figure 1 presents a sonogram of the first track from the album, *In Accordance*, whose duration is almost nine minutes. The analysis displays a clear delineation in frequency space in the 4 moments (or perhaps, sub-moments). The first moment (A) is comprised of a sustained 841 Hz pitch accented with a percussive "ping", which has a repetition rate of 7.2 Hz (8 beats at approximately 57 bpm). Typical of the album, Bissonnette's *oeuvre*, and the larger genre of post-ambient music, the track fades in; however, rather than slowly introducing constituent elements, the gestures seem to already exist, and are discretely brought to our attention. In Stockhausen's terminology, the work has started, but its beginning was long before.

After approximately one minute twenty seconds (B), the listener becomes aware of a new gesture in a higher frequency range: related (it is also percussive and a similar piano-like timbre), but comprised of a slightly different repetition cycle (1.8 Hz, or 32 bpm). Again, typical of Bissonnette, the two frequencies are related – a Just major sixth; the entire work explores the relationship between these two intervals without extending to a larger pitch set.

The introduction of lower frequencies at (C) is slightly more abrupt, seemingly causing one of the original frequency bands to become much less perceptible (although not disappear). A pair of high frequency beating gestures – centered around 2631 and 5386 Hz – as well as transient clicks (suggesting analog record noise) are introduced. The extreme high and low frequencies fade (A + B), revealing the original frequencies of the opening, without the percussive elements.

The proportions of the four sections, despite lacking clear divisions, have durational relationships that, while not exact, demonstrates Kramer's axiom of proportion being a seminal formal element in Moment-form (see Table 1). Although the final section may be considered as a return, it is perceived more as a reminder of earlier textures that never actually disappeared. Note that Stockhausen prohibits recapitulation in his articles, but return does appear in his music.

Fig. 1. Sonogram of Christopher Bissonnette's *In Accordance*. Frequency bands are highlighted in red; sub-moments between dotted lines, are lettered.

Section	Start time	Duration (sec)	Ratio
A	0:00	80	1.0
B	1:20	150	1.875
C	3:50	320	4.0
A + B	7:50	120	1.5

Table 1. Proportions in Bissonnette’s *In Accordance*

4. GENERATING MOMENT-FORM

As discussed in section 2, generating large-scale structure is a complex task, and remains an open-problem in musical metacreation [14]. Several aspects of Moment-form are thus compelling models for formal generation.

4.1 Generative Potential

4.1.1 Moments as parametric containers

The notion that individual moments should be comprised of unique organisational methods suggests generative potential. Smalley proposes that a composer utilising Moment-form “must be aware of all the potentialities of his material before he actually begins to notate the score”, which is often how designers of generative structures approach their material. He suggests that such organisational requirements account for Stockhausen’s “obsessive interest in the categorising and pre-compositional ordering of his basic material” [20]. Similarly, generative structures often involve parameterisation of a great deal of musical features, and individual moments can be delineated by unique constraints upon these methods.

4.1.2 Staticism

The consistency of features, to the point of staticism, is an interesting alternative to the model of continual evolution. While most contemporary music that can be considered “tonal” does not rely upon harmony to provide large-scale structure in the same way that composers of the 19th century used it in their goal-directed motion, it does, nonetheless, often exploit cyclical harmonic patterns to outline meso-structures and phrases. In these cases, higher-level forms are created by varying the harmonic cycles, generating typical song-forms (i.e. verse-chorus) or dance forms (A B C D permutations) [28]. Avoiding harmonic movement at the surface level avoids the need for harmonic change at the structural level, a device employed by contemporary ambient artists in their avoidance of all harmonic change. Instead, surface variation – and listener interest – is maintained by generating processes that explore timbral alteration (e.g. filter sweeps) or highlighting different pitch classes in a unvarying pitch set.

Generative practices are already being used in ambient electronica, although not always fully acknowledged. Marsen Jules (Martin Juhls), an exception to this, is a self-proclaimed generative electronic musician who has released ten albums whose music “modulates on the basis of strict rules...varying over and over and thus emerges from the very moment itself” [29], using techniques inspired by Steve Reich and Brian Eno. Juhls demonstrates a further trait of contemporary ambient artists’ take on

moment-form, in that he is interested in consistency, and avoids any contrast that may suggest discontinuity (personal communication).

4.2 Musebots

There have been many successful MuMe production systems that have generated complete musical works, and therefore generated long-term musical structure. As MuMe does not exclude human-machine interaction, these systems have tended to rely upon human-machine partnerships. More recently, creative research has been undertaken to collaboratively explore autonomous machine-machine generative systems through the use of specifically designed collaborative musical agents. Musebots [30] are autonomous musical agents that interact in performance, messaging their current states in order to allow other musebots to adapt. Recent musebots have been developed that broadcast their intentions, and not just their current state, thereby allowing other musebots to modify their own plans.

A particularly exciting aspect of musebots involves the notion that developers must decide *how* the musebots should interact, and *what* information is necessary to produce meaningful musical interaction. Musebots offer the potential to create complex musical surfaces and structures in which the organisation cannot be pointed to a single clever programmer. Naturally, concepts of formal design have been raised: initial musebot ensembles followed either a self-organising model, or a reactive model in which one musebot “took the lead” in determining sectional change. Musebot ensembles have thus far avoided the requirement of large-scale formal structures by limiting their performances to five to seven minute compositions.

5. MOMENTS

Musebots allow for a collective, collaborative approach to generative music production; however, as they require a consensus in what information is to be communicated, a singular design approach has proven to be more successful in exploring a particular compositional perspective. *Moments* is an ongoing installation using musebots created only by the author, in which continuous Moment-forms are generated, and subsequently explored sonically.

With each new composition, a *parameterBot* is initially launched that determines the next composition’s ensemble, selecting from pre-curated combinations of musebots. Each musebot has preferred generative tendencies, including timbral properties (i.e. synthesis techniques), frequency ranges (i.e. low versus high frequencies), and potential for background (i.e. drones) versus foreground (i.e. more transient) gestures.

Once a new ensemble of musebots has been launched, the *parameterBot* decides upon the overall compositional duration, and the number of sections (moments) contained within the work. Durations for each section are generated proportionally, with subsequent section being either in 2:3 or 3:2 durational relationships to the current section.

Parameter values for a variety of features are also calculated. These values can be considered as mean values within a constrained random range. Since the range is also generated and communicated, the combination of the two values is essentially a tendency mask for the feature over the duration of the section [31]. At the moment, features that are generated include:

- speed (tempo);
- activityLevel (relative density of events);
- voiceDensity (number of active voices);
- complexity (regarding harmony, melodic shape, syncopation);
- volume;
- consistency (amount of surface level change)
- pitch (mean pitch).

Messages are sent for each parameter within each section, with a start and end value for the section; thus, the same value for start and end assumes a consistent level during that section, while two different values assumes a linear movement between the two values (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2. *parameterBot* displaying a ten minute composition containing seven moments/sections, with the speed (thick line) and pitch parameters with surrounding tendency masks (thin lines) shown.

Once the values have been messaged to the musebot agents, the musebot Conductor is initiated, which provides a continuously running clock, beginning at time zero. Musebots use the clock time to determine their location in the overall form as well as the current section.

Surface features, including when to play, and how often events occur, are negotiated by the musebots themselves. Given the prescribed parameters – for example, activityLevel and voiceDensity – musebots continually communicate their current state, and to some extent, their future actions, thereby allowing other musebots to adjust their own activities.

The potential for autonomous musical agents to negotiate a requested feature value was explored within *Kinetic Engine* [32], albeit limited to rhythmic density. In that case, agents contained enough musical intelligence to generate correct musical responses that would vary depending upon other agent actions, as well as new requests from a Conductor (a human performer). The *Coming Together* series [33] explored autonomous requests without human interaction; however, overall form was dependent upon self-organisation, and not a request in itself. One goal for *Moments* is to use a Listener musebot that collects individual musebot activity, and compares the current states to the request from the *parameterBot*; the Listener bot would then send its own messages, informing the ensemble whether to adjust current parameters (i.e. more cowbell) depending upon inadequately negotiated targets.

6. FUTRE WORK AND CONCLUSION

Moments is in an early stage of what is clearly going to be a long-term project. Like all generative music, finding the “sweet spots” for parameter ranges, determining which parameters to automate, and the complex interaction between parameters, will require a great deal of listening to the output of the system. As Marsen Jules states, “Usually when I create this kind of music I listen to the set up for hours to explore all details that happen in the setting” [29].

Generative music, and its contemporary offspring, Musical Metacreation, offers composers the opportunity to explore processes and systems that create continually changing music. While generating large-scale structure remains an open problem in MuMe, exploring Moment-form avoids the (potentially unnecessary) complexities of traditional formal models, utilising instead the only new formal model invented since the dissolution of tonality over one hundred years ago: Moment-form. By actively seeking staticism, eschewing beginnings and endings, avoiding harmony as a structural feature, and emphasising timbre and frequency space as primary structural avenues, Moment-form offers a pragmatic alternative to traditional goal-based music, especially generative music.

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7. REFERENCES

- [1] P. Galanter, “What is Generative Art? Complexity theory as a context for art theory,” in *Generative Art Conference (GA 2003)*, Milan, 2003.

- [2] W. Berry, *Form in Music* (Vol. 1). Prentice-Hall, 1966.
- [3] E. Miranda, *Composing Music with Computers*. CRC Press, 2001.
- [4] A. Whittall, "Form," *Grove Music Online*. Oxford Music Online. Oxford University Press, accessed Feb. 1, 2016.
- [5] F. Salzer, *Structural hearing: Tonal Coherence in Music*. Courier Corporation, 1962.
- [6] J. Kramer, *The Time of Music New Meanings, New Temporalities, New Listening Strategies*. Schirmer Books, 1988.
- [7] A. Schoenberg and L. Stein, *Fundamentals of Musical Composition*. Faber & Faber, 1970.
- [8] P. Galanter, "Computational aesthetic evaluation: past and future," in *Computers and Creativity*, Springer Berlin, 2012, pp. 255–293.
- [9] R. Rowe, *Interactive Music Systems: Machine Listening and Composing*. MIT Press, 1992.
- [10] D. Cope, *Experiments in Musical Intelligence*. A-R Editions, 1996.
- [11] A. Eigenfeldt, "Generating Electronica - A Virtual Producer and Virtual DJ," in *Proceedings of the 9th ACM Conference on Creativity & Cognition*, Sydney, 2013, p. 396.
- [12] D. Conklin, "Music Generation from Statistical Models", in *AISB 2003 Symposium on Artificial Intelligence and Creativity in the Arts and Sciences*, Aberystwyth, 2003, pp. 30–35.
- [13] B. Smith and G. Garnett, "Improvising Musical Structure with Hierarchical Neural Nets," in *Proceedings of the Artificial Intelligence and Interactive Digital Entertainment Conference*, Palo Alto, 2012, pp. 63–67.
- [14] A. Eigenfeldt, "Generating Structure – Towards Large-Scale Formal Generation," in *Proceedings of the Artificial Intelligence and Interactive Digital Entertainment Conference*, Raleigh, 2014, pp. 2–9.
- [15] D. Cope, *The Algorithmic Composer*. A-R Editions, 2000.
- [16] P. Boulez, D. Noakes, and P. Jacobs, "Alea," in *Perspectives of New Music* 3(1), 1964, pp. 42–53.
- [17] T. Blackwell and M. Young, "Self-organised music", in *Organised Sound* 9(02), 2004, pp. 123–136.
- [18] E. Narmour, "The Top-down and Bottom-up Systems of Musical Implication: Building on Meyer's Theory of Emotional Syntax," in *Music Perception: An Interdisciplinary Journal* 9(1), 1991, pp. 1–26.
- [19] K. Stockhausen, "Momentform: Neue Beziehungen zwischen Aufführungsdauer, Werkdauer und Moment," in *Texte zur Musik* 1, 1963, pp. 189–210.
- [20] R. Smalley, "'Momente': Material for the Listener and Composer: 1," in *The Musical Times* 115 (1571), 1974, pp. 23–28.
- [21] J. Kramer, "Moment form in twentieth century music," in *The Musical Quarterly* 64(2), 1978, pp. 177–194.
- [22] J. Kramer, "The Fibonacci series in twentieth-century music," in *Journal of Music Theory* 17(1), 1973, 110–148.
- [23] R. Maconie, *The Works of Karlheinz Stockhausen*. Oxford University Press, 1976.
- [24] R. Parks, *The Music of Claude Debussy*. Yale University Press, 1989.
- [25] R. Orledge, "Understanding Satie's Vexations", in *Music & Letters* 79(3), 1998, 386–395.
- [26] B. Eno, *Ambient Music*. <http://www.iub.edu/~audioweb/T369/eno-ambient.pdf>, accessed April 11, 2016.
- [27] P. Shapiro, *Modulations: a history of electronic music: throbbing words on sound*. Distributed Art Publishers, 2000.
- [28] A. Eigenfeldt, and P. Pasquier, "Evolving structures for electronic dance music," in *Proceedings of the 15th annual conference on Genetic and evolutionary computation (GECCO 2013)*, 2013, pp. 319–326.
- [29] M. Juhles, *Marsen Jules*. <http://www.marsenjules.de/>, accessed April 18, 2016.
- [30] O. Bown, B. Carey, and A. Eigenfeldt, "Manifesto for a Musebot Ensemble: A platform for live interactive performance between multiple autonomous musical agents," in *Proceedings of the International Symposium of Electronic Art (ISEA 2015)*, 2015.
- [31] B. Truax, "Real-time granular synthesis with a digital signal processor," in *Computer Music Journal* 12(2), 1988, pp. 14–26.
- [32] A. Eigenfeldt, "Emergent rhythms through multi-agency in Max/MSP," in *Computer Music Modeling and Retrieval. Sense of Sounds*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2007, pp. 368–379.
- [33] A. Eigenfeldt, "Coming together: negotiated content by multi-agents," in *Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Multimedia*, Florence, 2010, pp. 1583–1586.

ⁱⁱ<https://open.spotify.com/album/0YzwNo517SNbNMITxRlt6p>